

Ion-exchange studies of resin copolymers derived from aromatic hydroxy compounds

S. C. Das

Department of Chemistry, S. V. M. College, Jagatsinghpur-754 103, India

Manuscript received 18 September 1998, revised 22 June 1999, accepted 20 August 1999

The ion-exchange capacity, effect of electrolytes on metal uptake, rate of metal uptake and distribution of metal ion at different pHs of resin copolymers derived from thiosemicarbazone derivatives of phenolic compounds shows higher order than the resin copolymer derived from semicarbazone derivatives. The results are compared with the commercial ion-exchangers.

Ion-exchange resins are porous synthetic organic polymers containing charged groups which are capable of holding positive and negative ions. In the present investigation the resin copolymers have been prepared from the polycondensation of resacetophenone thiosemicarbazone-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-formaldehyde (RATS-4HBA-F), resacetophenone semicarbazone-4-hydroxybenzoic acid-formaldehyde (RAS-4HBA-F), resacetophenonethiosemicarbazone-2-aminobenzoic acid-formaldehyde (RATS-2ABA-F) and resacetophenonesemicarbazone-2-aminobenzoic acid-formaldehyde (RAS-2ABA-F). Batch equilibrium method was utilised to study the ion-exchange properties of the resin copolymers.

Results and Discussion

The FTIR and NMR spectral data of the copolymers agree with that reported earlier¹.

Determination of effect of electrolyte on metal uptake : Perusal of data from Tables 1 and 2 reveals that the amount of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} taken by the resin increases with increasing concentration of Cl^- and NO_3^- ion, but decreases with increasing concentration of SO_4^{2-} . This may be explained on the basis of stability constants of the metal complexes². The ligand sulphates might be forming strong chelates with the above metal ions whereas the other metal ions form weak chelates.

Distribution studies : The distribution of the metal ions as the function of pH for different resin copolymers are presented in Table 2. The present investigation limits the distribution studies upto a certain pH for a metal ion to prevent the hydrolysis at higher pH. The data shown Table 3 indicate that no specific general trend is observed in mea-

Table 1. Effect of different electrolyte on the uptake of several metal ions for the resin copolymer RATS-4HBA-F

Metal ion	Electrolyte mol dm^{-3}	pH	mmol of metal ion uptake in presence of				
			NaCl	KCl	NaNO_3	KNO_3	Na_2SO_4
Co^{2+}	0.01	6	0.147	0.240	0.232	0.176	0.210
	0.05		0.158	0.256	0.248	0.192	0.186
	0.1		0.172	0.266	0.256	0.210	0.154
	0.5		0.210	0.282	0.284	0.222	0.148
Zn^{2+}	0.01	6	0.210	0.244	0.260	0.186	0.244
	0.05		0.236	0.266	0.282	0.198	0.212
	0.2		0.258	0.282	0.294	0.212	0.186
	0.5		0.266	0.296	0.310	0.242	0.156
Cu^{2+}	0.01	10	0.176	0.202	0.210	0.240	0.186
	0.05		0.192	0.230	0.224	0.258	0.152
	0.1		0.215	0.246	0.236	0.266	0.138
	0.5		0.235	0.252	0.258	0.278	0.128
Mg^{2+}	0.01	10	0.204	0.254	0.186	0.230	0.220
	0.05		0.232	0.268	0.210	0.256	0.204
	0.2		0.246	0.284	0.234	0.266	0.188
	0.5		0.266	0.292	0.250	0.280	0.162
Mn^{2+}	0.01	10	0.186	0.205	0.234	0.212	0.280
	0.05		0.198	0.237	0.266	0.234	0.248
	0.1		0.224	0.248	0.284	0.256	0.215
	0.5		0.236	0.268	0.290	0.275	0.198

Table 2. Effect of different electrolytes on the uptake of several metal ions for the resin copolymer RAS-4HBA-F

Metal ion	Electrolyte mol dm ⁻³	pH	mmol of metal ion uptake in presence of				
			NaCl	KCl	NaNO ₃	KNO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₄
Co ²⁺	0.01	6	0.058	0.049	0.046	0.054	0.171
	0.05		0.060	0.054	0.052	0.058	0.138
	0.1		0.065	0.057	0.052	0.061	0.129
	0.5		0.068	0.062	0.059	0.065	0.080
Zn ²⁺	0.01	6	0.054	0.053	0.050	0.053	0.148
	0.05		0.062	0.055	0.056	0.059	0.106
	0.2		0.066	0.062	0.060	0.063	0.061
	0.5		0.072	0.068	0.065	0.067	0.040
Cu ²⁺	0.01	10	0.027	0.025	0.017	0.057	0.126
	0.05		0.030	0.030	0.020	0.067	0.106
	0.1		0.032	0.017	0.026	0.076	0.076
	0.5		0.035	0.014	0.036	0.089	0.062
Mg ²⁺	0.01	10	0.037	0.042	0.046	0.039	0.172
	0.05		0.044	0.048	0.050	0.049	0.122
	0.2		0.053	0.052	0.055	0.047	0.104
	0.5		0.061	0.057	0.059	0.052	0.076
Mn ²⁺	0.01	10	0.080	0.071	0.062	0.066	0.098
	0.05		0.084	0.074	0.066	0.068	0.064
	0.1		0.085	0.077	0.068	0.074	0.062
	0.5		0.092	0.082	0.074	0.077	0.044

Table 3. Distribution ratio (*D*^{*}) of different metal ion as a function of pH for different resin copolymers

Time = 24 h, temp. = room temp.

Copolymer	Metal ion	Distribution ratio of metal ion at different pHs				
		2	3	4	6	8
RATS-2ABA-F	Co ²⁺	15.54	24.36	40.28	66.44	80.24
	Zn ²⁺	10.80	35.54	60.44	78.77	90.34
	Cu ²⁺	9.68	30.43	60.60	84.20	92.34
	Mg ²⁺	7.47	21.34	50.74	74.28	90.45
	Mn ²⁺	12.66	48.40	70.43	82.60	92.00
RAS-2ABA-F	Co ²⁺	23.44	33.21	59.32	75.38	80.20
	Zn ²⁺	11.44	27.60	50.50	70.44	80.60
	Cu ²⁺	15.20	30.50	50.46	72.62	84.30
	Mg ²⁺	6.75	22.45	44.60	68.44	84.45
	Mn ²⁺	10.75	30.20	50.44	68.76	85.75
RATS-4HBA-F	Co ²⁺	16.50	31.70	52.10	75.50	84.81
	Zn ²⁺	13.20	30.20	51.30	72.25	80.09
	Cu ²⁺	17.50	33.60	55.80	76.40	85.30
	Mg ²⁺	6.83	25.20	48.10	70.00	81.20
	Mn ²⁺	8.50	28.10	49.27	70.30	88.44
RAS-4HBA-F	Co ²⁺	11.20	12.20	19.50	28.80	40.20
	Zn ²⁺	20.20	35.40	48.40	62.10	95.80
	Cu ²⁺	6.18	9.20	22.40	65.80	81.20
	Mg ²⁺	35.20	60.50	96.00	110.20	180.59
	Mn ²⁺	8.40	22.50	52.30	71.20	88.50

$$D^* = \frac{\text{mmol of metal ion in the copolymer}}{\text{mmol of metal ion in the solution}} \times \frac{\text{vol. of solution}}{\text{wt. of copolymer}}$$

Table 4. Comparison of rate of metal uptake of different resin copolymers

Copolymer	Metal ion	Percentage of metal ion uptake at different time (h)							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
RATS-2ABA-F	Co ²⁺	32	38	45	54	62	75	88	95
	Zn ²⁺	22	30	42	54	65	71	85	94
	Cu ²⁺	28	40	54	60	72	78	84	100
	Mg ²⁺	30	44	52	68	76	82	88	98
	Mn ²⁺	20	30	45	48	58	66	75	91
RAS-2ABA-F	Co ²⁺	32	52	70	83	91	95	98	–
	Zn ²⁺	22	44	60	72	84	90	94	97
	Cu ²⁺	18	39	55	68	77	84	88	90
	Mg ²⁺	21	31	37	51	62	85	94	97
	Mn ²⁺	30	52	71	82	90	92	95	98
RATS-4HBA-F	Co ²⁺	38	42	46	55	63	68	76	93
	Zn ²⁺	35	40	52	58	64	70	85	96
	Cu ²⁺	42	48	56	62	74	84	92	99
	Mg ²⁺	28	35	47	55	66	75	86	94
	Mn ²⁺	34	43	56	66	74	86	92	99
RAS-4HBA-F	Co ²⁺	21	35	47	56	67	87	95	–
	Zn ²⁺	12	23	32	40	45	67	71	84
	Cu ²⁺	17	36	52	63	72	81	88	93
	Mg ²⁺	23	32	42	48	54	66	70	74
	Mn ²⁺	32	57	75	87	93	97	100	–

asuring distribution coefficients but the distribution coefficient (D^*) increases with increasing atomic numbers except the case of Mg²⁺. These selectivity patterns can be qualitatively explained by the concept of the hard and soft acids and bases. Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ have low distribution ratios at pH 2–4. This is attributed to the low stability constant, i.e. weak ligand stabilisation energy of the complexes, according to Irving and Williams³.

The possible order of selectivity of a cation exchange resin for divalent metal ion is Pd²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Cd²⁺ > Fe²⁺ > Mn²⁺ > Mg²⁺. The reported resin copolymer showing the order of distribution ratio of divalent ions measured in the range pH 2–8 was found to be Co²⁺, Zn²⁺ > Mn²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Mg²⁺. This change is the observed trend may be due to the principle of selectivity.

Rate of metal uptake: Perusal of data in Table 4 reveals comparison of the rate of metal uptake of different resin copolymers at different time intervals. The rates of metal adsorption of the resins were determined to ascertain the shortest time period for which equilibrium could be carried out. The role of physical core structure of the resins is significant in the uptake of different metal ions by the resin copolymers. A perusal of the results (Table 4) indicates that Mg²⁺ and Mn²⁺ require almost 7 h for attaining equilibrium whereas Co²⁺ and Zn²⁺ require more than 8 h for

attaining the same. This agrees with the hardness properties of the metal ions which increase with increasing atomic number. It is of interest to note that the adsorption behaviour of metal ions increases with the increase in atomic number by the resin copolymers.

Hence, the study reveals that the resin copolymers prepared from thiosemicarbazone derivatives have higher order of adsorption than the semicarbazone derivatives, which is evident due to the fact that the molecular surface area of the resin might have increased with the incorporation of the sulphur atom in the thiosemicarbazone derivatives.

Experimental

By the standard methods of condensation⁴, the resin copolymers were prepared by condensing semicarbazone, thiosemicarbazone of various hydroxyacetophenones with substituted benzoic acids in presence of formaldehyde using acids as catalysts. The dried resin was treated with excess 5 N HCl followed by 5 N NaCl to convert the resins to Na⁺-form⁵. It was then purified by repeated washings with water and dried form in vacuum. All the chemicals and solvents used were of AnalaR grade and double-distilled before use.

Determination of exchange capacity: The dry resin (0.025 g) was kept in four different glass stoppered Erlen-

meyer flask. Constant pH was maintained by adding proper buffer solution followed by the addition of NaCl electrolyte solutions of strength 0.01, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.5 M respectively. The volume of each solution was kept constant at 40 ml. To it 1 ml of metal ion solution (0.1 M) was added to each flask. The contents were stirred and kept in a water-bath at 30° for ~24 h. After the selected time, it was shaken well, filtered and the filtrate along with washings was then titrated against 0.01 M EDTA solution using appropriate indicator. The same procedure was adopted by using other electrolytes, viz. NaNO₃, KCl, KNO₃ and Na₂SO₄. A blank experiment was also run simultaneously. The difference of which accounted for the exchange capacity of the resin copolymers.

Distribution coefficient of metal ion at different pHs :

The distribution coefficient of metal ion uptake of the resin in the presence of particular electrolyte was found out at equilibrium state at different pH values ranging from 2 to 8. By knowing the volume of EDTA consumed for the titration of metal ion solution in presence of electrolytes such as NaCl, NaNO₃, KCl, KNO₃, Na₂SO₄ in absence of resin,

the distribution coefficient was calculated by using the expression,

$$K_D = \frac{\text{mmol of metal ion in resin}}{\text{mmol of metal ion in soln}} \times \frac{\text{wt. of solution in ml}}{\text{wt. of the resin in mg}}$$

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Prof. P. L. Nayak, Ravenshaw College, and Principal, S. V. M. College, for facilities.

References

- 1 S C Das, S Lenka and P L Nayak, *J Polym Mater* 1997, 14, 219
- 2 F A Cotton and G Wilkinson, "Advance Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed, Interscience, New York, 1972, S I Davadov and N A Plate, *Coord Chem Rev* 1975, 16 195
- 3 H R Irving and R J Williams, *Chem Rev*, 1956 56, 271
- 4 P K Mohanty and S Lenka, *J Appl Polym Sci*, 1991, 42 2261
- 5 M Senapati, S P N S Burma and P L Nayak, *J Appl Polym Sci*, 1992, 45, 521